

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 69

Rev. Dr. Michael Harvey Koplitz

The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 69

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 69:0 For the choir director; according to †Shoshannim. <i>A Psalm</i> of David.</p>	<p>Psa. 69:1 לְמִנְצֵחַ עַל־שׁוֹשָׁנִים לְדָוִד : 2 הוֹשִׁיעֵנִי אֱלֹהִים כִּי</p>
<p>Psa. 69:1 Save me, O God, For the “waters have ¹threatened my life. ² I have sunk in deep “mire, and there is no foothold; I have come into deep waters, and a ^{1b}flood overflows me. ³ I am “weary with my crying; my throat is parched; My ^beyes fail while I wait for my God. ⁴ Those “who hate me without a cause are more than the hairs of my head; Those who would ¹destroy me ^bare powerful, being wrongfully my enemies; “What I did not steal, I then have to restore.</p>	<p>בָּאוּ מַיִם עַד־נַפְשִׁי : 3 טָבַעְתִּי אֲבִינֹן מְצוּלָה וְאֵין מָעַמָּד בָּאתִי בְּמַעַמְקֵי־מַיִם וְשִׁבְלֹת שִׁטְפֹתַי : 4 יִגְעַתִּי בְּקָרְאִי נִחַר גְּרוֹנִי כָּלוּ עֵינָי מִיַּחַל לְאֱלֹהֵי : 5 רַבּוּ מִשְׁעָרוֹת רֵאשֵׁי שְׂנְאָי הַנֶּגַם עָצְמוּ מְצַמִּיתִי אֵיבֵי שִׁקָּר אֲשֶׁר לֹא־גִזְלֹתִי אִזּוּ אָשִׁיב : 6 אֱלֹהִים אַתָּה יַדְעָתָ לְאֵינִלֹּתִי וְאֲשַׁמּוֹתִי מִמֶּנֶּה לֹא־נִכְחָדוּ : 7 אֶל־יִבְשׁוּ בִי אֶקְוֶה אֲדַגֵּי יְהוָה צָבָאוֹת אֶל־יִפְלְמוּ בִי מִבְּקִשְׁיָךְ אֱלֹהֵי יִשְׂרָאֵל : 8 כִּי־עָלִיךָ נִשְׂאתִי חֲרָפָה כִּסְתָּה כְּלִמָּה פָּנָי : 9 מוֹזֵר תִּיִיתִי לְאֶחָי וְנִכְרִי לְבָנֵי אֲמִי : 10 כִּי־קִנְאַת בֵּיתְךָ אֶכְלֹתַנִי וְחַרְפוֹת חוֹרְפִיךָ</p>
<p>Psa. 69:5 O God, it is You who knows “my folly, And ^bmy wrongs are not hidden from You. ⁶ May those who wait for You not “be ashamed through me, O Lord ¹GOD of hosts; May those who seek You not be dishonored through me, O God of Israel, ⁷ Because “for Your sake I have borne reproach; ^bDishonor has covered my face.</p>	<p>7 אֶל־יִבְשׁוּ בִי אֶקְוֶה אֲדַגֵּי יְהוָה צָבָאוֹת אֶל־יִפְלְמוּ בִי מִבְּקִשְׁיָךְ אֱלֹהֵי יִשְׂרָאֵל : 8 כִּי־עָלִיךָ נִשְׂאתִי חֲרָפָה כִּסְתָּה כְּלִמָּה פָּנָי : 9 מוֹזֵר תִּיִיתִי לְאֶחָי וְנִכְרִי לְבָנֵי אֲמִי : 10 כִּי־קִנְאַת בֵּיתְךָ אֶכְלֹתַנִי וְחַרְפוֹת חוֹרְפִיךָ</p>

⁸ I have become ^aestranged ¹from my brothers

And an alien to my mother's sons.

⁹ For ^azeal for Your house has consumed me,

And ^bthe reproaches of those who reproach You have fallen on me.

¹⁰ When I wept ^ain my soul with fasting,

It became my reproach.

¹¹ When I made ^asackcloth my clothing,

I became ^ba byword to them.

¹² Those who ^asit in the gate talk about me,

And I *am* the ^{1b}song of the drunkards.

Psa. 69:13 But as for me, my prayer is to You, O LORD, ^aat an acceptable time;

O God, in the ^bgreatness of Your loving-kindness,

Answer me with ¹Your saving truth.

¹⁴ Deliver me from the ^amire and do not let me sink;

May I be ^bdelivered from ¹my foes and from the ^{2a}deep waters.

¹⁵ May the ^{1a}flood of water not overflow me

Nor the deep swallow me up,

Nor the ^bpit shut its mouth on me.

Psa. 69:16 Answer me, O LORD, for ^aYour loving-kindness is good;

^bAccording to the greatness of Your compassion, ^cturn to me,

¹⁷ And ^ado not hide Your face from Your servant,

נִפְלֹוּ עָלַי : 11 וְאַבְכָּה בְצֹם

נִפְשִׁי וַתְּהִי לַחֲרָפוֹת לִי : 12

וְאַתָּנָה לְבוֹשֵׁי שֹׁק וְאַהֲרִי

לָהֶם לְמַשָּׁל : 13 יִשְׂיחוּ בִי

וְשָׁבִי שֹׁעַר וְנִגְיִנוֹת שׁוֹתֵי

שִׁכָּר : 14 וְאַנִּי תִפְלֵתִי-לָךְ |

יְהוָה עֵת רְצוֹן אֱלֹהִים בְּרָב-

חַסְדֶּךָ עֲנֵנִי בְּאַמֶּת יִשְׁעֶךָ : 15

הַצִּילֵנִי מִטִּיט וְאֶל-אֲטִבְעָה

אֲנַצֶּלֶה מִשָּׁנְאֵי וּמִמְעַמְקֵי-

מַיִם : 16 אֶל-תִּשְׁטַבְּנִי |

שִׁבְלֵת מַיִם וְאֶל-תִּבְלַעֲנִי

מִצֹּלָה וְאֶל-תִּאֲטַר-עָלַי

בְּאֵר פִּיָּה : 17 עֲנֵנִי יְהוָה כִּי-

טוֹב חַסְדֶּךָ כָּלֵב רַחֲמֶיךָ

פָּנָה אֵלַי : 18 וְאֶל-תִּסְתַּר

פָּנֶיךָ מִעַבְדֶּךָ כִּי-צָר-לִי

מִתֵּר עֲנֵנִי : 19 קָרְבָה אֶל-

נִפְשִׁי גְאֹלָה לְמַעַן אֵיבִי

פְּדֵנִי : 20 אֶתָּה יְדַעַת חֲרָפְתִּי

וּבְשׁוֹתֵי וּכְלִמְתֵי נִגְדֶךָ כָּל-

צוּרְרֵי : 21 חֲרָפָה אֲשַׁבֵּרָה

לְבִי וְאֶאֱנוּשָׁה וְאַקְנוֹת לָנוֹד

For I am ^bin distress; answer me quickly.

¹⁸ Oh draw near to my soul *and* ^aredeem it;

^bRansom me because of my enemies!

¹⁹ You know my ^areproach and my shame and my dishonor;

All my adversaries are ¹before You.

Psa. 69:20 Reproach has ^abroken my heart and I am so sick.

And ^bI looked for sympathy, but there was none,

And for ^ccomforters, but I found none.

²¹ They also gave me ^{1a}gall ²for my food

And for my thirst they ^bgave me vinegar to drink.

Psa. 69:22 May ^atheir table before them become a snare;

And ^{1b}when they are in peace, *may it become* a trap.

²³ May their ^aeyes grow dim so that they cannot see,

And make their ^bloins shake continually.

²⁴ ^aPour out Your indignation on them,

And may Your burning anger overtake them.

²⁵ May their ^{1a}camp be desolate; May none dwell in their tents.

²⁶ For they have ^apersecuted him whom ^bYou Yourself have smitten,

And they tell of the pain of those whom ^cYou have ¹wounded.

²⁷ Add ^ainiquity to their iniquity,

וְאִיִן אֶל־מִנְחָמִים וְלֹא

מִצָּאתִי : ²² וַיִּתְּנוּ בְּבִרוֹתַי

רֹאשׁ אֶל־צַמְאֵי יִשְׁקוּנִי חֶמְץ :

²³ יְהִי־שִׁלְחָנָם לְפָנֵיהֶם לְפַח

וְלִשְׁלוֹמִים לְמוֹקֵשׁ : ²⁴

תַּחֲשַׁכְנָה עֵינֵיהֶם מִרְאוֹת

וּמִתְנִיָּהֶם תִּמְרֵד תִּמְעַד : ²⁵

שִׁפְךָ־עַל־יָהֶם זַעֲמֶךָ וַתִּרְוֶן

אֶפְךָ יִשְׁיִגְם : ²⁶ תַּהִי־טִירְתָם

נִשְׁמָה בְּאֶהְלֵיהֶם אֶל־יְהִי

יָשֵׁב : ²⁷ כִּי־אַתָּה אֲשֶׁר־

הַכִּיתָ רִדְפוֹ וְאֶל־מִכְאוֹב

תִּלְלֶיךָ יִסְפְּרוּ : ²⁸ תִּנָּה־עוֹן

עַל־עוֹנָם וְאֶל־יָבֹאוּ

בְּצַד־קִלְתְּךָ : ²⁹ יִמְחוּ מִסֶּפֶר

תֵּימִים וְעַם צְדִיקִים אֶל־

יִכָּתְבוּ : ³⁰ וְאֲנִי עָנִי וְכוֹאֵב

יִשׁוּעַתְךָ אֱלֹהִים תִּשְׁגְּבֵנִי : ³¹

אַהֲלֵלְהָ שֵׁם־אֱלֹהִים בְּשִׁיר

וְאֲגִדְלֶנּוּ בְּתוֹדָה : ³² וְהִיטֵב

לִיהוָה מִשׁוֹר פֶּר מִקָּרָן

מִפְּרִיס : ³³ רָאוּ עֵגְוִים

יִשְׁמְחוּ דֹרְשֵׁי אֱלֹהִים וַיִּתִּי

And ^bmay they not come into
^cYour righteousness.

²⁸ May they be ^ablotted out of the
^bbook of life

And may they not be ^{1c}recorded
with the righteous.

Psa. 69:29 But I am ^aafflicted
and in pain;

¹May Your salvation, O God, ^bset
me *securely* on high.

³⁰ I will ^apraise the name of God
with song

And ^bmagnify Him with
^cthanksgiving.

³¹ And it will ^aplease the LORD
better than an ox

*Or a young bull with horns and
hoofs.*

³² The ^ahumble ¹have seen *it and* are
glad;

You who seek God, ^blet your
heart ²revive.

³³ For ^athe LORD hears the needy
And ^bdoes not despise His *who are*
prisoners.

Psa. 69:34 Let ^aheaven and
earth praise Him,

The seas and ^beverything that
moves in them.

³⁵ For God will ^asave Zion and
^bbuild the cities of Judah,

That they may dwell there and
^cpossess it.

³⁶ The ^{1a}descendants of His servants
will inherit it,

And those who love His name ^bwill
dwell in it.

לְבַבְכֶם : כִּי־שָׁמַע אֱלֹ-
אֲבִיוֹנִים יְהוָה וְאֶת־אֲסִירָיו
לֹא בָזָה : יְהִלְלוּהוּ שָׁמַיִם
וְאֶרֶץ יַמִּים וְכָל־רֹמֵשׁ בָּם :
כִּי אֱלֹהִים אִיזְשִׁיעַ צִיּוֹן
וַיְבַנֶּה עָרֵי יְהוּדָה וַיָּשְׁבוּ אָשֶׁם
וַיִּרְשׁוּהָ : וַיִּזְרַע עֲבָדָיו
יִנְחַלוּהָ וְאֶהְבֵּי שְׁמוֹ יִשְׁכְּנוּ-
בָהּ :

References

Psalm 69:0

[†]Or possibly *Lilies*

Psalm 69:1

¹Lit *come to the soul*

^aJob 22:11; Ps 32:6; 42:7; 69:14, 15; Jon 2:5

Psalm 69:2

¹Lit *flowing stream*

^aPs 40:2

^bJon 2:3

Psalm 69:3

^aPs 6:6

^bDeut 28:32; Ps 38:10; 119:82, 123; Is 38:14

Psalm 69:4

¹Or *silence*

^aPs 35:19; John 15:25

^bPs 35:19; 38:19; 59:3

^cPs 35:11; Jer 15:10

Psalm 69:5

^aPs 38:5

^bPs 44:21

Psalm 69:6

¹Heb *YHWH*, usually rendered *LORD*

^a2 Sam 12:14

Psalm 69:7

^aJer 15:15

^bPs 44:15; Is 50:6; Jer 51:51

Psalm 69:8

¹Lit *to*

^aJob 19:13-15; Ps 31:11; 38:11

Psalm 69:9

^aPs 119:139; John 2:17

^bPs 89:41, 50; Rom 15:3

Psalm 69:10

^aPs 35:13

Psalm 69:11

^{a1} Kin 20:31; Ps 35:13

^{b1} Kin 9:7; Job 17:6; Ps 44:14; Jer 24:9

Psalm 69:12

¹Lit *songs*

^aGen 19:1; Ruth 4:1

^bJob 30:9

Psalm 69:13

¹Or *the faithfulness of Your salvation*

^aPs 32:6; Is 49:8; 2 Cor 6:2

^bPs 51:1

Psalm 69:14

¹Lit *those who hate me*

²Lit *deep places of water*

^aPs 69:2

^bPs 144:7

Psalm 69:15

¹Lit *stream*

^aPs 124:4, 5

^bNum 16:33; Ps 28:1; 141:7

Psalm 69:16

^aPs 63:3; 109:21

^bPs 51:1; 106:45

Ps 25:16; 86:16

Psalm 69:17

^aPs 27:9; 102:2; 143:7

^bPs 31:9; 66:14

Psalm 69:18

^a2 Sam 4:9; Ps 26:11; 49:15

^bPs 119:134

Psalm 69:19

¹Or known *to You*

^aPs 22:6; 31:11

Psalm 69:20

^aJer 23:9

^bPs 142:4; Is 63:5

^cJob 16:2

Psalm 69:21

¹Or *poison*

²Or *in*

^aDeut 29:18

^bMatt 27:34, 48; Mark 15:23, 36; Luke 23:36; John 19:28-30

Psalm 69:22

¹Lit *for those who are secure*

^aRom 11:9, 10

^{b1}Thess 5:3

Psalm 69:23

^aIs 6:10

^bDan 5:6

Psalm 69:24

^aPs 79:6; Jer 10:25; Ezek 20:8; Hos 5:10

Psalm 69:25

¹Lit *encampment*

^aMatt 23:38; Luke 13:35; Acts 1:20

Psalm 69:26

¹Lit *pierced*

^{a2}Chr 28:9; Zech 1:15

^bIs 53:4

^cPs 109:22

Psalm 69:27

^aNeh 4:5; Ps 109:14; Rom 1:28

^bIs 26:10

^cPs 103:17

Psalm 69:28

¹Lit *written*

^aEx 32:32, 33; Rev 3:5

^bPhil 4:3; Rev 13:8; 17:8; 20:15

^cPs 87:6; Ezek 13:9; Luke 10:20; Heb 12:23

Psalm 69:29

¹Or *Your salvation, O God, will set...*

^aPs 70:5

^bPs 20:1; 59:1

Psalm 69:30

^aPs 28:7

^bPs 34:3

^cPs 50:14

Psalm 69:31

^aPs 50:13, 14; 51:16

Psalm 69:32

¹Some mss and ancient versions read *will see*

²Or *live*

^aPs 34:2

^bPs 22:26

Psalm 69:33

^aPs 12:5

^bPs 68:6

Psalm 69:34

^aPs 96:11; 98:7; 148:1-13; Is 44:23; 49:13

^bIs 55:12

Psalm 69:35

^aPs 46:5; 51:18

^bPs 147:2; Is 44:26

‘Obad 17

Psalm 69:36

¹Lit *seed*

^aPs 25:13; 102:28

^bPs 37:29

Targum

Psa. 69:1 For praise; concerning the exiles of the Sanhedrin; composed by David. ² Redeem me, O God, for an army of sinners has come to trouble me, like water that has reached to the soul. ³ I am sunk in exile like water of the deep, and there is no place to stand; I have come to the mighty depths; a band of wicked men and a wicked king have sent me into exile. ⁴ I am weary of calling out, my throat has become rough, my eyes have ceased to wait for my God. ⁵ Those who hate me without a cause are more numerous than the hairs of my head; those who dismay me – my enemies, false witnesses – have grown strong; what I never stole I will [have to] repay, because of their false witness. ⁶ O God, you know my folly; my sins have not been hidden from your presence. ⁷ Those who trust in you will not be disappointed in me; those who seek instruction from you will not be ashamed of me, O God of Israel. ⁸ For on your account I have borne disgrace; shame has covered my face. ⁹ I have been accounted a stranger to my brothers, and [I am] like a Gentile to the sons of my mother. ¹⁰ For zeal for the sanctuary has consumed me; and the condemnation of the wicked who condemn you when they prefer their idols to your glory has fallen on me. ¹¹ And I wept in the fasting of my soul; and my kindness became my shame. ¹² And I put sackcloth in place of my clothing; and I became a proverb to them. ¹³ Those who sit in the gate will speak about me in the marketplace, and [in] the songs of those who come to drink liquor in the circuses. ¹⁴ But as for me, my prayer is in your presence, O LORD, in the time of favor; O God, in the abundance of your goodness answer me in the truth of your redemption. ¹⁵ Deliver me from exile, which is likened to mud, and I will not sink; let me be delivered from my enemies, who are like the depths of waters. ¹⁶ A mighty king will not send me into exile, and the powerful deep will not swallow me to cover me up, and the mouth of Gehenna will not be opened up for me. ¹⁷ Answer me, O LORD, for your kindness is good; look towards me with the abundance of your compassion. ¹⁸ And do not remove your presence from your servant, for I am in distress; hasten, answer me. ¹⁹ Draw near to my soul, redeem it, so that my enemies may not claim superiority over me, redeem me. ²⁰ You know my disgrace and my shame and my dishonor; before you stand all my oppressors. ²¹ Disgrace has broken my heart, and behold, it is ill; and I waited for those skilled in mourning, but they were not; and for those skilled in comfort, and I found them not. ²² And as my meal they gave me bitter gall and poison; and for my thirst, they gave me vinegar to drink. ²³ Let their table that they set before me with my food become a snare before them; and their sacrifices an offense. ²⁴ Let their eyes darken so they cannot see, and let their loins continually tremble. ²⁵ Pour out your anger upon them, and may your harsh anger overtake them. ²⁶ Let their tent become deserted, may no one settle in their tent. ²⁷ For they have pursued the one you have smitten, and they shall tell of the one wounded for your slain. ²⁸ Give iniquity for their iniquity, and let them not be purified to enter the assembly of your righteous ones. ²⁹ Let them be erased from

the memorial book of life, and let them not be written with the righteous. ³⁰ But I am poor and wounded; your redemption, O God, will save me. ³¹ I will praise the name of my God with song, and I will magnify him with thanksgiving. ³² And my prayer will be more pleasing in the presence of the LORD than a choice fatted ox that the first Adam sacrificed, whose horns preceded its hooves. ³³ The humble have seen; so let those who seek instruction from the presence of God be glad and let their heart live. ³⁴ For the LORD accepts the prayer of the lowly, and has not despised his prisoners. ³⁵ Let the angels of heaven and those who dwell on earth praise him; the seas, and all that swarms in them. ³⁶ For God will redeem Zion and repair the cities of Judah, and they will return thither and inherit it. ³⁷ And the sons of his servants will succeed to it, and those who love his name will abide in its midst.

Spiritual Awareness

Due to the length of the Psalm, only the spiritual awareness of verses will be explored.

Introduction

Jewish history is that even though the people were exiled from their homeland, thus living on foreign soil for centuries, the nation grew and prospered. In 1948 the nation of Israel was reestablished on the land that the LORD promised to give Abraham and his descendants.

A rose is delicate and protected by the thorns that surround it. This is a metaphor for Israel. She is delicate and is protected by the Torah, which surrounds her. This Psalm is a prophetic vision of David that generations of brave Jews survived the dark centuries of exile.

Superscript

The Psalmist reminds Israel that she is in danger of attack and that only the LORD can protect her.

To the Sefirah Netzach who offers victory, upon roses, by David.

Verse one

David is saying that a whirlpool plunging into the deep had grabbed him and was taking him down. He was in dire need of the LORD to save his soul. The depths would have taken him to Sheol.

Help me, O God, for the waters have penetrated unto my soul.

Verse four

Israel did not find sympathy from the nations of the world. The nations that housed hostile feelings against her were ready to destroy her. The Psalmist requested the ability to restore Israel after her enemies ruined her.

They that hate me without reason are more than the hairs of my head; mighty are they that would make me numb, that unjustly come forward as my foes so that I might restore that which I have never taken away.

Verse eight

David was speaking for Israel. It is acknowledged that the other nations of the world are also the children of the LORD because the LORD is the Father of all humanity, and therefore, they should have recognized Israel as a sister nation.

I became to my brothers as a man unworthy of rights and an alien to the sons of my mother.

Verse thirteen

David calls out to the Sefirah Chesed for the LORD's loving-kindness.

But as for me, my prayer shall be to You, O God, for one instant of favor; O God, who even while judging remains in the abundance of loving kindness from the Sefirah Chesed, answer me with the truth of Your salvation.

Verse eighteen

The redemption of Israel by the LORD teaches the nations of the world that they, too, need to examine their morals and ethics so that the godless humans will not ruin them.

Draw nearer to my soul, and redeem it; ransom me because of my enemies.

Verse twenty-three

With the sensual depravity of the nations, they will lose the clarity of spiritual perception.

That their eyes may become darkened so that they cannot see and let their loins tremble continually.

Verse thirty

The nations that conquered Israel thought that the LORD had abandoned them. When the Babylonians invaded Judah, it was not much of a fight. They believed that the LORD had abandoned Israel. However, Israel never lost faith in the LORD.

But as far for me, afflicted and in pain, Your salvation, O God, shall set me up on high.

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

MHK V5 1/17/2016

Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

MHK V1.1 6/23/14

